

Bioassay of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Nomuraea rileyi* (Deuteromycotina; Hyphomycetes) against the rice leaffolder (LF)

R.M. Aguda, Entomology Department, IRRI, and M.C. Rombach, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research, Ithaca, New York, USA

Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia* spp. are infected with various entomogenous fungi, including *Beauveria bassiana*, *Nomuraea rileyi*, *Paecilomyces farinosus*, and an unidentified entomophthorean species. These fungi are obligate insect pathogens that might be useful in biological control of LF.

We tested the virulence of *B. bassiana* (white muscardine fungus) and *Nomuraea rileyi* (cosmopolitan pathogen of lepidoptera) on LF *C. medinalis*. The *B. bassiana* isolate originated from the brown planthopper from China, the *N. rileyi* isolate originated from hairy caterpillar *Rivula atimeta* in the Philippines.

Suspensions of 0, 10⁴, 10⁵, 10⁶, 10⁷, and 10⁸ conidia/ml were prepared for both fungi. Thirty 3d-instar LF larvae were dipped in each suspension and left for several minutes on filter paper. Treated larvae were incubated in petri

Mortality of LF larvae treated with different entomogenous fungi. IRRI, 1987.

dishes containing rice leaves; the leaves were renewed daily. Mortality was determined after 1 wk incubation.

Mortality percentage was adjusted, using Abbott's formula. Differences between fungi species were tested by probit analysis. Probit analysis resulted

in ED₅₀ of 7.4 × 10³ conidia/ml for *B. bassiana* and ED₅₀ of 3.5 × 10⁵ conidia/ml for *N. rileyi*.

Virulence of these fungi differed (see figure). The *B. bassiana* isolate was more infectious to this host. □

Effect of buprofezin in controlling green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) incidence

S. Mas'ud, and Moeh, Sudjak S., Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia

We evaluated an insect growth regulator, buprofezin, in the field against *Nephotettix virescens* GLH population and RTV infection.

Two formulations were used: wettable powder (WP) and emulsifiable concentrate (EC), each at 250, 500, and 1,000 g (ml)/ha. The trial was conducted at Maros in the dry season and at Lanrang in the 1986 wet season in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 ×

Table 1. GLH population and RTV incidence at Maros, Indonesia, 1986.

Buprofezin concentration g (ml)/ha	Formulation	GLH ^a (no./40 hills)		Tungro incidence (%)	
		28 DT	49 DT	56 DT	63 DT
250	10 WP	12.7 a	7.0 a	51	83
500	10 WP	13.2 a	12.7 ab	60	78
1000	10 WP	11.5 a	5.7 a	54	81
250	400 EC	14.0 ab	11.0 ab	49	79
500	400 EC	21.7 b	14.5 ab	53	83
1000	400 EC	14.2 ab	8.0 a	45	68
0 (control)	—	36.7 c	20.0 b	66	87

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P 0.05.

10 m. Variety Cisadane was planted at 25 × 25-cm spacing. Urea and TSP were applied at 40 kg N and 18 kg P/ha 25 and 50 d after transplanting (DT). The insecticide was applied first when GLH was found on trial plots. Counts were made from 1 d after insecticide

application to 49 DT in Maros and 53 DT in Lanrang. RTV incidence was monitored weekly until symptoms were found.

At Maros, GLH was found 21 DT at 8-17 insects/40 hills. At 28 DT, all insecticide rates significantly controlled

GLH (Table 1). By 35 DT, the rates did not significantly differ from each other.

RTV was 45-65% at 56 DT and increased to 68-88% by 63 DT. All insecticide rates tested kept GLH below the economic injury level of 25 insects/hill, but did not prevent RTV.

At Lanrang, GLH was found 48-56 insects/40 hills at 18 DT (Table 2). All insecticide rates tested were ineffective at 25 and 32 DT, but were effective at 39 DT, By 53 DT, treatments were not significantly different from each other. Severe RTV infection was found at 60 DT. All treatments were ineffective in

Table 2. GLH population and RTV incidence at Lanrang, Indonesia, 1986.

Buprofezin concentration (g (ml)/ha)	Formulation	GLH ^a (no./40 hills)		Tungro incidence (%) 60 DT
		25 DT	46 DT	
250	10 WP	44.7 ab	19.7 ab	99
500	10 WP	30.2 ab	15.5 a	96
1000	10 WP	39.5 ab	17.5 a	98
250	400 EC	40.7 ab	17.5 a	98
500	400 EC	51.2 b	20.7 ab	97
1000	400 EC	28.0 a	17.7 a	95
0 (control)	-	74.5 c	26.7 b	99

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P 0.05.

suppressing RTV. Buprofezin is slow to control GLH populations because it acts

only during molting. The delay allows RTV to be transmitted. □

Knockdown of green leafhopper (GLH) by six insecticides

R.F. Macatula and O. Mochida, IIRRI

Some insecticides that control GLH effectively do not always prevent tungro (RTV) infection. This is probably due to slow knockdown, as GLH can transmit RTV before it dies. Using foliar spray and contact toxicity tests, we evaluated four pyrethroids, one carbamate, and one organophosphate in the laboratory for quick knockdown.

In the foliar spray test, 30-d-old potted seedlings of highly susceptible TNI were cleaned, placed on an electrically rotating table, and uniformly sprayed with insecticide, using an Arthur Thomas sprayer. Spray rates were 0.005, 0.15, and 0.01% ai. Control plants were sprayed with distilled water.

Ten minutes after treatment (MAT), the mylar film-caged plants were infested with 20 GLH adults. Knockdown mortalities were recorded up to 24 h after insect release.

In the contact toxicity test, 20 GLH adults were collected from rearing cages, anaesthetized with CO₂ gas for 10 s, and transferred onto petri dishes lined with filter paper. The dishes were placed at the bottom of a Potter's spray tower and sprayed with insecticide solution.

Treated adults were transferred to 15-d-old untreated TNI seedlings. Mortality was recorded to 60 MAT.

With foliar spraying, adult mortalities

Table 1. Effect of foliar spraying of 6 insecticides on *N. virescens* adults. IIRRI insectary, 1986.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (% ai)	Adult female mortality (%) at indicated time after release ^b		
		1 h	3 h	24 h
Alphamethrin	0.01	77 c	79 b	90 b
Cypermethrin	0.01	100 a	100 a	100 a
Ethoproxyfen	0.01	100 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	0.15	98 b	100 a	100 a
Monocrotophos	0.15	79 c	100 a	100 a
Deltamethrin	0.005	100 a	100 a	100 a
Control	-	0 d	0 c	0 c

^aSpray volume based on 500 liters water/ha. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Effect of contact spray of 6 insecticides on *N. virescens* adults. IIRRI insectary, 1986.

Insecticide ^a	Rate (% ai)	Adult female mortality (%) at indicated time after treatment ^b			
		5 min	10 min	20 min	60 min
Alphamethrin	0.01	2 cd	4 c	15 c	16 c
Cypermethrin	0.01	70 a	92 a	100 a	100 a
Ethoproxyfen	0.01	15 b	21 b	36 b	49 b
MIPC	0.15	2 cd	4 c	0 d	19 c
Monocrotophos	0.15	5 cd	4 c	2 d	2 de
Deltamethrin	0.005	79 a	95 a	100 a	100 a
Control	-	0 d	0 c	0	0 e

^aSpray volume based on 500 liters water/ha. ^bAv of 4 replications, 20 GLH/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

were significantly high with all 6 insecticides 1 h after release (Table 1). With direct spraying, the synthetic

pyrethroids deltamethrin and cypermethrin showed significantly higher knockdown 5 MAT (Table 2).

Effect of synthetic pyrethroid insecticides on green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV)

S.L. Valencia and O. Mochida, IIRRI

We evaluated 4 synthetic pyrethroids — ethoproxyfen (0.1 kg ai/ ha), cypermethrin (0.05 kg ai/ ha), alphamethrin, and deltamethrin (0.0125 kg ai/ ha) — for *Nephotettix virescens* GLH and